

Best ways of teaching English language

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Annotation: This article discusses the convenient and high-quality ways to learn English and all foreign languages.

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Teaching a foreign language can be a challenging but rewarding job that opens up entirely new paths of communication to students. It's beneficial for teachers to have knowledge of many different language learning techniques including ESL teaching methods so they can be flexible in their instruction methods, adapting them when needed.

Keep on reading for all the details you need to know about the most popular foreign language teaching methods. Some of the ones covered are the communicative approach, total physical response, the direct method, task-based language learning, suggestopedia, grammar-translation, the audio-lingual approach and more.

According to academic research, linguists have demonstrated that there is not one single best method for everyone in all contexts, and that no one teaching method is inherently superior to the others.

Also, it is not always possible – or appropriate – to apply the same methodology to all learners, who have different objectives, environments and learning needs.

Applying the most appropriate method for that learner's specific objectives, learning style and context.

An experienced professional language teacher always adopts the Principled Eclecticism approach, deciding on the most suitable techniques and applying the most appropriate methodology for that learner's specific objectives, learning style and context.

Methods of teaching English have developed rapidly, especially in the previous 40 years. As a language learner, training manager, or teacher, it is important to understand the various methods and techniques so that you are able to navigate the market, make educated choices, and boost your enjoyment of learning a language. Each

teaching method is based on a particular vision of understanding the language or the learning process, often using specific techniques and materials used in a set sequence.

The main methodologies are listed below in the chronological order of their development:

Grammar Translation – the classical method

Direct Method – discovering the importance of speaking

Audio-lingualism – the first modern methodology

Humanistic Approaches – a range of holistic methods applied to language learning

Communicative Language Teaching – the modern standard method

Principled Eclecticism – fitting the method to the learner, not the learner to the method

In the direct method, all teaching occurs in the target language, encouraging the learner to think in that language. The learner does not practice translation or use their native language in the classroom. Practitioners of this method believe that learners should experience a second language without any interference from their native tongue. Instructors do not stress rigid grammar rules but teach it indirectly through induction. This means that learners figure out grammar rules on their own by practicing the language. The goal for students is to develop connections between experience and language. They do this by concentrating on good pronunciation and the development of oral skills. This method improves understanding, fluency, reading, and listening skills in our students. Standard techniques are question and answer, conversation, reading aloud, writing, and student self-correction for this language learning method. As mentioned above, the modern language teacher doesn't follow one rigid method, but applies the Principled Eclecticism approach – fitting the method to the learner, not vice versa.

This means choosing the techniques and activities that are appropriate for each particular task, context and learner, with a focus on motivation and helping learners become independent and inspired to learn more.

The explanation of Principled Eclecticism also includes a useful ten-point guide for teachers and language students on the best teaching and learning techniques.

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References:

1. N.I. Gez, M.V. Lyakovitskaya, A.A. Mirolyubov. Methodology of teaching foreign languages
2. IMPORTANCE OF ATTENTION IN PRESCHOOLERS' COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT TO PROGRESS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE Iminova Xumora Mukhammadisa kizi 2020/7 EPRA International Journal of Research and Development Том 5 Номер 7 Страницы 101-103 Издатель EPRA JOURNALS
3. "Methodology of foreign language teaching" - Jamal Jalolov. Teacher Publishing House, 1996.

